

Atomic mass estimates for proposed Elements 119 - 127

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In a previous article [1], chemical elements were shown re-aligned in a Table that is actually Periodic:

1 H Hydrogen																		
2 He Helium	3 Li Lithium	4 Be Beryllium	5 B Boron	6 C Carbon	7 N Nitrogen	8 O Oxygen	9 F Fluorine	10 Ne Neon	11 Na Sodium	12 Mg Magnesium	13 Al Aluminum	14 Si Silicon	15 P Phosphorus	16 S Sulphur	17 Cl Chlorine	18 Ar Argon	19 K Potassium	
20 Ca Calcium	21 Sc Scandium	22 Ti Titanium	23 V Vanadium	24 Cr Chromium	25 Mn Manganese	26 Fe Iron	27 Co Cobalt	28 Ni Nickel	29 Cu Copper	30 Zn Zinc	31 Ga Gallium	32 Ge Germanium	33 As Arsenic	34 Se Selenium	35 Br Bromine	36 Kr Krypton	37 Rb Rubidium	
38 Sr Strontium	39 Y Yttrium	40 Zr Zirconium	41 Nb Niobium	42 Mo Molybdenum	43 Tc Technetium	44 Ru Ruthenium	45 Rh Rhodium	46 Pd Palladium	47 Ag Silver	48 Cd Cadmium	49 In Indium	50 Sn Tin	51 Sb Antimony	52 Te Tellurium	53 I Iodine	54 Xe Xenon	55 Cs Cesium	
56 Ba Barium	57 La Lanthanum	58 Ce Cerium	59 Pr Praseody...	60 Nd Neodymium	61 Pm Promethium	62 Sm Samarium	63 Eu Europium	64 Gd Gadolinium	65 Tb Terbium	66 Dy Dysprosium	67 Ho Holmium	68 Er Erbium	69 Tm Thulium	70 Yb Ytterbium	71 Lu Lutetium	72 Hf Hafnium	73 Ta Tantalum	
74 W Tungsten	75 Re Rhenium	76 Os Osmium	77 Ir Iridium	78 Pt Platinum	79 Au Gold	80 Hg Mercury	81 Tl Thallium	82 Pb Lead	83 Bi Bismuth	84 Po Polonium	85 At Astatine	86 Rn Radon	87 Fr Francium	88 Ra Radium	89 Ac Actinium	90 Th Thorium	91 Pa Protactinium	
92 U Uranium	93 Np Neptunium	94 Pu Plutonium	95 Am Americium	96 Cm Curium	97 Bk Berkelium	98 Cf Californium	99 Es Einsteinium	100 Fm Fermium	101 Md Mendelevium	102 No Nobelium	103 Lr Lawrencium	104 Rf Rutherfordium	105 Db Dubnium	106 Sg Seaborgium	107 Bh Bohrium	108 Hs Hassium	109 Mt Meitnerium	
110 Ds Darmstadtium	111 Rg Roentgenium	112 Cn Copernicium	113 Nh Nihonium	114 Fl Flerovium	115 Mc Moscovium	116 Lv Livermorium	117 Ts Tennessine	118 Og Oganesson	119 X1	120 X2	121 X3	122 X4	123 X5	124 X6	125 X7	126 X8	127 X9	

This left room for nine more Elements, of atomic numbers 119 - 127. To estimate their atomic mass, a 3rd order polynomial fit through the known mass values [2] produced reasonable results; in the figure below, the top tier plots mass vs. atomic #, while the lower tier shows fit residuals.

With this fit, mass estimates for Elements 119-127 were:

EL119: 300.375; EL120: 302.560; EL121: 304.721; EL122: 306.857; EL123: 308.969; EL124: 311.055;
 EL125: 313.117; EL126: 315.151; EL 127: 317.161.

[1] <https://zenodo.org/records/19804658>

[2] <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ptable/atomic-mass/>